

Pre-print version

Final version published in Transplantation: DOI: 10.1097/TP.00000000000005210

**TITLE. Requesting relatives' consent for intensive care for organ donation:
An empirical analysis of Spanish transplant coordinators' practices**

Rubén García-Sánchez, PhD^c

María Soria-Oliver, PhD^a

Jorge S. López, PhD, MD^{a,b}

José M. Martínez, PhD^c

Alberto Barceló, PhD^b

María J. Martín, PhD^c

Elisabeth Coll, MD^d

José Roldán, MD^e

David Uruñuela, MSN^f

Alberto Fernández-Carmona, MD^g

^aDepartamento de Ciencias de la Salud, Universidad Pública de Navarra,
Campus de Arrosadia, 31006 Pamplona, Navarra, Spain

^bInstituto de Investigación Sanitaria de Navarra, Recinto del Hospital
Universitario de Navarra, Calle Irunlarrea, 3, 31008 Pamplona, Navarra, Spain

^cFacultad de Psicología, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Ciudad Universitaria
de Cantoblanco, 28049 Madrid, Spain

^dOrganización Nacional de Trasplantes, Calle Sinesio Delgado 6-8, Pabellón 3,
28029 Madrid, Spain

^eCoordinación Autonómica de Trasplantes de Navarra, Complejo Hospitalario de
Navarra, Calle Irunlarrea, 3 Chalet Adona, Pamplona 31008, Navarra, Spain

^fCoordinación de Trasplantes, Hospital Universitario Puerta de Hierro. C/Manuel
de Falla, 1, Majadahonda 28222, Madrid, Spain

^gHospital Universitario Virgen las Nieves, Ctra Jaén s/n, Granada 18013, Spain

CORRESPONDENCE

Jorge S. López Departamento de Ciencias de la Salud, Universidad Pública de
Navarra, Campus de Arrosadia, 31006, Pamplona, Navarra, Spain

Email: jorge.lopez@unavarra.es

AUTHORSHIP

Rubén García-Sánchez participated in research design, fieldwork, and data analysis.

María Soria-Oliver participated in research design, fieldwork, and manuscript writing.

Jorge S. López acted as research coordinator and participated in research design, fieldwork, analysis quality control, and manuscript writing.

José M. Martínez participated in research design, fieldwork, and data analysis.

Alberto Barceló participated in data analysis and manuscript writing.

María J. Martín participated in research design and fieldwork.

Elisabeth Coll participated in research design and sample recruitment and assessed intensive care to facilitate organ donation (ICOD) procedures throughout the study.

José Roldán participated in fieldwork and assessed ICOD procedures throughout the study.

David Uruñuela participated in research design and sample recruitment and assessed ICOD procedures throughout the study.

Alberto Fernández-Carmona participated in research design and elaborated the ICOD flow chart diagram.

All authors reviewed the manuscript.

DISCLOSURE

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

FUNDING

This study was funded by Instituto de Salud Carlos III, project number PI18/00403), and co-funded by the European Regional Development Fund and European Social Fund (“Investing in your future”).

ABBREVIATIONS

BD, brain death

CDCDD, controlled donation after the circulatory determination of death.

DCDD, donation after the circulatory determination of death.

DBD, donation after brain death.

EI, early interview.

ICOD, intensive care to facilitate organ donation.

ICU, intensive care unit.

TCT, transplant coordination team.

MV, mechanical ventilation.

SM, support measure.

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: Intensive care to facilitate organ donation (ICOD) involves the initiation or continuation of intensive care for patients with devastating brain damage to incorporate the option of donation after brain death in end-of-life care. Obtaining family consent for ICOD differs from standard family consent interviews, as relatives are approached to discuss the possibility of donation before the patient's death. Considering the lack of previous studies on family consent interviews for ICOD, this work aimed to analyze how transplant coordinators in Spain interact with relatives when requesting family consent for ICOD.

METHODS: Semi-structured interviews were conducted with a random stratified sample of 23 Spanish transplant coordination teams (TCTs) to explore strategies, practices, and perceptions of ICOD consent requests. Interviews were recorded, transcribed, and analyzed using content analysis.

RESULTS: Family interviews to request ICOD consent is a standardized procedure for coordination teams and involves a highly professional and diversified set of strategies. Coordination with other units and retrieval of information regarding the relatives' emotional and informational states are crucial. Confirming the relatives' understanding of the patient's fatal prognosis is a vital starting point. ICOD discussions involve listening, providing emotional support, offering clear and continuous information, managing time effectively, and exploring patients' will.

CONCLUSIONS: Approaching families to obtain consent for ICOD is developed as a regular and structured practice of TCTs in Spain. Our study provides a

diverse range of strategies that serve as reference for obtaining consent from families for ICOD in other settings.

1. Introduction

Donor shortage is a major factor limiting the ability to fulfill organ transplantation demands at an international level.¹ To reduce the imbalance between organ supply and demand, organ procurement organizations have promoted a wide range of initiatives to improve organ donation rates—including procedures to expand the potential donor pool, optimization of potential donors' identification and referral rates, expansion of donor eligibility criteria, improvement of organ preservation techniques, and development of policies to increase positive responses to donation requests.¹⁻³ A recent strategy involves the implementation of intensive care to facilitate organ donation (ICOD), which refers to the initiation or continuation of intensive care in patients with devastating brain damage when treatment with curative intent has been abandoned, aiming to include the possibility of donation after brain death (DBD) in end-of-life care plans.⁴ ICOD seeks to improve donation rates by increasing the number of patients in adequate condition to allow for DBD. Additionally, ICOD facilitates discussions with relatives regarding the possibility of controlled donation after the circulatory determination of death (CDCDD) if the patient does not progress to brain death (BD) and hospital resources allow it.⁴⁻⁶

The ICOD procedure has been implemented in several Western countries⁶⁻⁹; however, Spain stands out for the progressive development of this procedure in an increasing number of hospitals.¹⁰⁻¹³ The relevance of ICOD for obtaining donations was first demonstrated in a multicenter study conducted in

Spain.¹⁴ Currently, the available data indicate that 36.5% (696/1905) of the total donations in Spain were obtained in 2021 through the ICOD procedure.¹⁵

ICOD development is supported by comprehensive ethical and legal frameworks and consensual practice protocols in Spain.^{4,16} Thus, ICOD can expand the potential donor pool and improve the survival and quality of life of patients requiring transplants. Moreover, ICOD helps fulfill patients' wills if they favor organ donation. Consequently, discussing the option of ICOD with relatives is seen as the duty of professionals responsible for the care of patients' last wills and rights.^{4,10,16}

Implementing ICOD in Spain requires obtaining family consent through an early interview (EI).¹⁷ In the EI, relatives are approached by transplant coordination teams (TCTs) after the diagnosis of devastating brain injury to request consent for the implementation or maintenance of elective mechanical ventilation (MV) and support measures (SMs) aimed at facilitating organ donation. Figure 1 presents a global view of the phases, pathways, and potential outcomes involved in the ICOD procedure. It has been self-elaborated based on existing works on this topic^{4-6,10,11,13} ICOD can be implemented in various scenarios with varying levels of difficulty in clinical management and family approach.^{16,18} Scenarios wherein the patient is in the intensive care unit (ICU) under MV generally involve stable clinical situations and previous interactions with relatives. This allows more flexibility in the timing of request for consent for ICOD from the family, taking into consideration the relatives' emotional and situational conditions. Conversely, patients outside the ICU, usually in the emergency unit, and without MV instauration, generally present unstable clinical situations and limited interaction with relatives. This hinders adequate time

management for the family approach and creates worse conditions for requesting consent for ICOD.

- FIGURE 1 -

In contrast to family interviews for DBD, EI involves TCTs initiating discussions about donation with relatives before the patient passes away. Therefore, relatives must decide regarding possible donation based on the patient's fatal prognosis rather than death. EI is also a different scenario from family interviews for donation after the circulatory determination of death (DCDD), since families are asked by TCTs to provide consent for the maintenance or implementation of MV and SMs with the specific goal of enabling a potential donation. This necessitates additional waiting time from relatives before the patient's final evolution occurs. Consequently, the decision regarding donation in the context of ICOD is affected by circumstances that differ from other family interview scenarios: it takes place in a different temporal sequence and time margin, it provokes discussion about donation in an earlier stage of the family grief process, and it requires a waiting period from relatives in which events about the relative's evolution are uncertain. All these factors may affect different processes that, according to the existing evidence, are key for family decision. Among them stand relatives' expectations regarding the clinical prognosis of the patient when donation has to be discussed, time margin available to make a decision, and intensity of relatives' emotional reactions to the patient's situation.¹⁹⁻²⁴

The literature analyzing effective practices of TCTs in providing support to families and obtaining consent for donation is extensive. However, existing studies on this topic focus on donation scenarios that are already well-

established, primarily analyzing the DBD scenario and, to a lesser extent, the DCDD scenario.²²⁻²⁷ Although consensus documents on ICOD provide guidance on conducting EIs based on the existing general knowledge about the family grief process and family interviews,^{4,16,18} to our knowledge, no study has empirically identified the practices of TCTs in developing requests for family consent for ICOD. Considering that ICOD is already a rarely implemented procedure in most national contexts, it is crucial to provide empirical guidance on how to approach families and request consent in this scenario. Therefore this study aimed to provide a first approach to the characterization of the process of obtaining family consent for ICO by means of identifying Spanish TCTs' practices and perceptions of it, including perceptions of the process of identification of ICOD candidates, strategies for preparation, initiation and development of EIs, strategies to cope with potential denial of consent, potential events and follow-up interventions between ICOD consent and effective donation, and perceptions of the reasons for family refusal. Findings of this investigation can therefore offer structured guidelines for developing EIs for ICOD, which could serve as reference for other transplantation systems.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Design

This study employed a cross-sectional design with qualitative data retrieval and quantitative content analysis of textual data.

2.2 Setting

Spanish hospitals with donation activity who have effectively implemented ICOD procedures to obtain donation of solid organs before 2018.

2.3 Information collection technique

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with TCT members. The interview script is available in the Supplemental Digital Content.

2.4 Population

We included all TCTs involved in ICOD procedures in Spanish hospitals.

2.5 Sample

The study used a stratified random sample of 23 (of the 51) TCTs involved in ICOD procedures in Spain in 2018 (Table 1). The sample size was defined to ensure the inclusion of at least one TCT in all selected geographical strata. Further, this sample was considered adequate to attain proper data variability according to the team's previous research on TCT practices²⁸ and evidence from qualitative studies on healthcare practices.²⁹ In the first stage, the interviews were stratified across 17 Spanish autonomous communities proportionate to the estimated annual number of donations obtained through the ICOD. In the second stage, the specific hospital centers of each stratum (autonomous community) were assigned by random proportional selection, with the estimated number of annual ICOD donations as the criterion. The data provided by Spain's National Transplant Organization for 2018 were used. All initially selected TCTs agreed to participate in the interviews. The selected centers obtained 371 of the 618 ICOD donations registered in Spain in 2018.

- INSERT TABLE 1 -

2.6 Interview contents

The interviews explored the practices and perceptions of TCTs relating to the ICOD procedure. In this work, a summary of relevant contents is presented, including the identification of candidates for ICOD, strategies for preparing the EI, verbal and non-verbal strategies for beginning the EI, strategies and arguments for EI development, indicators of potential family refusal and strategies to handle it, perceptions about reasons for family refusal of consent, events and actions in the period between ICOD implementation and effective donation, and estimation of the percentage of family consent to the ICOD procedure.

As mentioned, the difficulty of family approach in EI varies.^{16,18} For this study's purposes, in order to focus our findings in those scenarios that differ from the most common donation procedures, the respondents were asked to describe their practices and perceptions regarding difficult scenarios.

2.7 Procedure

TCTs were identified through mediation by the National Transplant Organization staff, who explained the study's objectives and enquired regarding TCTs' availability. Subsequently, a member of the research team associated with the university centers made contact and arranged interviews with each TCT. Of the 23 interviews, 16 were conducted in person at the hospital center of the TCT, six were conducted virtually using Zoom® and Skype® because of the COVID-19 pandemic, and one was a mixed interview (initiated face-to-face and completed virtually at a different time). Interviewers guaranteed that no one was present during interviews except participants and researchers. Each interview was conducted by a research team member, with five interviewers (one woman and four men) participating in the information collection. The interviewers were senior researchers, university professors, and Ph.D. physicians in psychology

with no connection to the transplant system. Fifteen interviews were conducted with a single member of the TCT, and eight were conducted with two or more members (six with two interviewees, one with three interviewees, and one with four interviewees). The interviewees comprised 17 men and 17 women; 28 were intensive care physicians, and six were intensive care nurses. The average duration of interviews was 121 minutes, with a range of 49–226 minutes. Before the interview, TCTs members were provided the study information sheet and directed to express their informed consent. Emphasis was placed on the guarantees of confidentiality of the information collected, ensuring that results would be processed without reference to specific hospital centers. The interviews were recorded with the consent of the TCTs and were transcribed for analysis. Additionally, the interviewers filled a brief field report to register participants' characteristics, interview climate, duration, and any other relevant aspects after completing the interview. The research team's members reviewed the transcripts. The possibility of the TCTs reviewing the transcripts was ruled out owing to workload saturation. Fieldwork was conducted from July 2019 to September 2021.

2.8 Analysis and quality control

The texts of the interviews were analyzed using content analysis,^{30,31} which is a research technique for making replicable and valid inferences from texts. Content analysis was applied to reduce the textual information by codification into structured topics (first-level of codification) and categories (second level of codification). The first codification was conducted using a preconfigured topic structure derived from the interview script and included the main areas explored in the interviews (Figure 2). The second level of coding was

generated inductively by analyzing specific answers. Coding was conducted, verified, and reformulated by three members of the research team through an inter-rater consensus system using a Delphi panel procedure. This was selected to generate a highly specific code system with a low level of inference, whereby the code tags were close to the literalness of the response. This system offers a lower condensation of information and direct presentation of the results through a descriptive frequency analysis, reducing the level of subjectivity. The number of codes for answers to open questions vary depending on the extent of answers obtained. This system prioritizes obtaining a broad overview over assessing the frequency of each code.

- FIGURE 2 -

The final coding was subjected to quality control by another member of the research team, who performed independent coding of a random selection of nodes. Mean inter-rater reliability (kappa index of 0.81/1) was 0.73–1.00, indicating good or very good reliability, particularly considering the exploratory-descriptive character of the present study.^{32,33} N-Vivo® V.12 (QSR-International-Lumivero, Denver, CO, USA) was used for qualitative analysis.

The sample achieved an adequate representation of population data based on (1) the sample size relative to total population size (23/51 Spanish TCTs participating in ICOD procedures; TCTs responsible for 371/618 ICOD donations registered in Spain in 2018); (2) high specificity of the subject of study; (3) sample diversity regarding participant characteristics, number of yearly ICOD donations, and geographical origin; and (4) level of redundancy regarding central topics of the retrieved information regarding TCTs' experiences and perceptions.

An initial report of the methodology and results was sent to the 23 participating TCTs and two experts from the National Transplant Organization for review and suggestions for possible modifications. Suggestions were received from two TCTs; additionally, various terminological suggestions from the National Transplant Organization experts were incorporated into the final version. This study followed the consolidated criteria for reporting qualitative research (COREQ).³⁴ The checklist of fulfillment of the 32 COREQ criteria is included in the Supplemental Digital Content.

2.9 Ethical considerations

All participants were provided the study information sheet and directed to provide their informed consent. Emphasis was placed on the guarantees of confidentiality of the information collected. This study was approved by the ethics, animal experimentation, and biosafety committee of the Public University of Navarre (number PI-020/18).

3. RESULTS

Tables 2–10 present the contents and frequency of codes identified using content analysis. As the answer length varied, several codes could be included in the same category. Interview excerpts are provided in the Supplemental Digital Content.

- TABLES 2–10 -

Most respondents stated that ICOD candidates can be reliably identified, with the lack of familiarity with the procedure among other hospital units and potential medical contraindications being the biggest obstacles (Table 2). EI preparation focuses on ensuring the family's understanding and acceptance,

offering emotional support, and making it possible to obtain donations (Table 3). Coordination with other units is significant, particularly for understanding information previously provided to the family and their emotional state (Table 3). TCTs develop actions to ensure appropriate interview location and review available medical information (Table 3). Knowing the patient's will is important; therefore, several TCTs consult official records of last wills and the patient's family (Table 4). TCTs deploy various strategies in EIs (Table 5). Verbal communication strategies include making the family aware of the patient's irreversible situation, introducing him/herself as transplant coordinator to the family, identifying the main decision makers, and offering empathy and support by understanding the family's needs (Table 5). Non-verbal strategies include maintaining physical closeness with family members and adapting to their characteristics (Table 5). Providing information and resolving doubts are essential during EI, and inquiring about the patient's will and family's desire increases the likelihood of donation (Table 6). TCTs propose donation based on the possibility of helping other people, supporting the patient's wishes, noting that donation is a rare opportunity rather than an obligation, and explaining that donation can help cope with the loss (Table 7). TCTs develop actions based on indicators of potential refusal, including offering more time, emphasizing the benefits of donation, and continuing to resolve potential doubts (Table 8). The biggest obstacles between ICOD consent and effective donation are family perceptions that the waiting time is excessive and emergence of new circumstances, such as the appearance of new decision makers (Table 9). Therefore, TCTs prioritize offering the withdrawal of VM/SMs, raising the possibility of proceeding with the CDCDD, or prolonging the waiting time (Table

9). The percentage of family consent to ICOD is generally high, with the patient's negative or unknown will being the most frequent reason for refusal (Table 10).

4. DISCUSSION

This study analyzed the practices of Spanish TCTs in obtaining consent for ICOD, including candidate identification, strategies for preparing and conducting EI, and subsequent actions. Findings in the existing literature offer the first empirical systematization of the way in which TCTs develop the family approach in this recently developed donation scenario. The results reflected highly professional work in the process of obtaining family consent for ICOD. This study identified specific actions in the preparation, initiation, development, and follow-up of the request process. The level of formalization of these strategies differed depending on the team; however, a wide set of resources was implemented in all cases. These results reflect in the specific procedure of ICOD the professionalization evidenced in other Spanish TCTs' donation procedures, which have been repeatedly linked to successful donation rates.^{2,35,36}

Our findings indicated that coordinated action between TCTs and other health personnel is key to obtaining donations through the ICOD. Coordination affects the ability to retrieve initial data from units outside the ICU, whose personnel may be unfamiliar with donation procedures.^{37,38} Furthermore, coordination influences EI preparation and development, which require knowledge of information provided to the family and their emotional states. Coordination between professionals is essential for obtaining family consent,^{2,39,40} particularly for ICOD owing to the difficult conditions that this strategy may entail.

Initiation and development of EIs for ICOD exhibit similarities and differences with family interviews in the DBD scenario. Although the communication of the patient's death in the case of BD can produce doubts, uncertainty, and a lack of adjustment among family members,^{22,25,41-43} the EI for ICOD starts from a fatal prognosis. Thus, information regarding prior communications between the family and other physicians and the family's level of understanding, reaction, and degree of adjustment is required. This information determines the contents that can be discussed with the family, interview timing, and pertinence of raising the possibility of donation. Therefore, the results indicated that pronouncing the fatal prognosis is essential in the initial interview development. Following this pronouncement, TCTs manage interview contents to ensure that ICOD discussion is initiated only after a basic comprehension of the situation has been reached and the emotional states of relatives fulfill the minimum conditions to cope with the ICOD proposal.

Discussing organ donation with relatives before the patient's death is a controversial issue in donation literature and may be a barrier to ICOD. Previous studies have found that "decoupling"—that is, placing the discussion of donation in a separate and posterior moment of the notification of death—is associated with higher consent rates^{44,45}; however, other studies have failed to demonstrate this association^{20,46} or found better consent rates when donation was mentioned before the pronouncement of death.^{47,48} In light of these results, several authors have highlighted that the appropriate timing for an organ donation request depends on the degree to which the relatives have accepted the irreversibility of the patient's death, regardless of the official pronouncement of death.^{19,47,49} This implies that practitioners should not take decoupling as the main criterion for

performing an adequate request but should, instead, tactfully follow the family's emotional process to mention donation when the patient's death is seen by the family as a definitive and irreversible fact.^{19,24} Our findings indicated that mentioning the possibility of donation before the pronouncement of death is an established and regular practice among the TCTs, who considered the adequacy of this practice to be based on prior information, support, empathy, and respect for opportune emotional moments, regardless of the pronouncement of death.

TCT practices to develop EIs include elements similar to those in successful donation requests in other scenarios.^{24,26,40,50} This includes dialogue with decision makers, listening, providing emotional support, relaying clear and continuous information, determining the appropriate time to approach families for donation requests, and presenting arguments based on solidarity. ICOD procedures differ from those of other donations in the waiting period for BD. Factors that appear during this waiting period may affect the family's initial consent. Therefore, follow-up, reevaluation, and support actions are required to preserve the well-being of relatives and maximize the final possibility of donation.

This study had some limitations. First, this study examined the subjective accounts—rather than objective records—of TCTs regarding their practices. Although the guarantee of confidentiality and use of appropriate interview strategies, such as open questions, mirror communication, and lack of valuation,⁵¹ facilitated obtaining valid information, the effects of social desirability and subjective re-elaboration of TCTs' own experiences could not be eliminated. Second, the interviews collected the most salient perceptions that came to the interviewees' minds; however, other practices may have existed, which were not expressed in the interviews. Moreover, interviewees could provide more or less

extensive details of their strategies, thereby generating differences between teams. Thus, the results should be mainly interpreted as an extensive identification and systematization of Spanish TCTs' strategies and resources when performing EIs for ICOD, granting the absolute frequencies of different categories only an indicative value. Future studies that aim to characterize and improve strategies for performing EI for ICOD requests should complement transplant coordinator views with a systematic registration of their practices and a quantitative examination of their relationship with families' decision and perceived support.

Seemingly, EIs for ICOD are a standardized practice among the interviewed TCTs, requiring coordination with other health professionals and structured strategies. EIs require listening, providing information, and showing support prior to requesting consent for ICOD. This approach to family consent by establishing a helping relationship is important for ICOD and has traditionally defined the activity of Spanish TCTs in other donation procedures.^{52,53} Perceiving ICOD as both a part of patients' end-of-life care and an opportunity to improve public quality of life by facilitating donation can promote the involvement of TCTs from other contexts in EIs for ICOD, thereby increasing the organ donation pool.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was possible by the participation of members of the following TCTs, who contributed their knowledge and experience through interviews: H. Universitario Virgen Macarena (Sevilla), H. Universitario Reina Sofía (Córdoba), Hospital Regional Universitario de Málaga, H. Universitario Miguel Servet (Zaragoza), H. Universitario Central de Asturias (Oviedo), H. Universitario Son

Espases (Palma de Mallorca), H. de Gran Canarias Doctor Negrín, H. Universitario Insular de Gran Canaria, H. Universitario Marqués de Valdecilla (Santander), H. Universitario Virgen de la Salud (Toledo), Complejo Asistencial de Burgos, H. Universitario Vall d'Hebrón, H. Universitario de Girona Dr. Josep Trueta, H. Infanta Cristina (Badajoz) Complejo Hospitalario Universitario de Santiago de Compostela, H. San Pedro (Logroño), H. Universitario Gregorio Marañón (Madrid), H. Universitario Ramon y Cajal (Madrid), H. Universitario de la Princesa (Madrid), H. Universitario Virgen de la Arrixaca (Murcia), H. Universitario de Navarra, H. Universitario de Arraba (Vitoria), and H. Universitario Dr. Balmis (Alicante). We would like to thank Prof. Mark Beyebach for his contribution during the initial phase of the project and Ricardo Lamelas for his technical support throughout the project.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION STATEMENT

Additional information is available online in the Supporting Information section as Supplementary Digital Content.

REFERENCES

1. Lewis A, Koukoura A, Tsianos GI, Gargavanis AA, Nielsen AA, Vassiliadis E. Organ donation in the US and Europe: The supply vs demand imbalance. *Transplant Rev.* 2021;35(2). doi:10.1016/j.trre.2020.100585
2. Vanholder R, Domínguez-Gil B, Busic M, et al. Organ donation and transplantation: a multi-stakeholder call to action. *Nat Rev Nephrol.* 2021;17(8):554-568. doi:10.1038/s41581-021-00425-3
3. Vanholder R, Stel VS, Jager KJ, et al. How to increase kidney transplant activity throughout Europe - An advocacy review by the European Kidney Health Alliance. *Nephrology Dialysis Transplantation.* 2019;34(8):1254-1261. doi:10.1093/ndt/gfy390

4. Martín-Delgado MC, Martínez-Soba F, Masnou N, et al. Summary of Spanish recommendations on intensive care to facilitate organ donation. *American Journal of Transplantation*. 2019;19(6):1782-1791. doi:10.1111/ajt.15253
5. Domínguez-Gil B, Coll E, Elizalde J, et al. Expanding the Donor Pool Through Intensive Care to Facilitate Organ Donation: Results of a Spanish Multicenter Study. *Transplantation*. 2017;101(8):e265-e272. doi:10.1097/TP.0000000000001701
6. Manara A, Procaccio F, Domínguez-Gil B. Expanding the pool of deceased organ donors: the ICU and beyond. *Intensive Care Med*. 2019;45(3):357-360. doi:10.1007/s00134-019-05546-9
7. Melville A, Kolt G, Anderson D, Mitropoulos J, Pilcher D. Admission to intensive care for palliative care or potential organ donation: Demographics, circumstances, outcomes, and resource use. *Crit Care Med*. 2017;45(10):e1050-e1059. doi:10.1097/CCM.0000000000002655
8. Nelson HM, Glazier AK, Delmonico FL. Changing Patterns of Organ Donation: Brain Dead Donors Are Not Being Lost by Donation after Circulatory Death. *Transplantation*. 2016;100(2):446-450. doi:10.1097/TP.0000000000000954
9. Witjes M, Kruijff PEV, Haase-Kromwijk BJJM, van der Hoeven JG, Jansen NE, Abdo WF. Physician Experiences with Communicating Organ Donation with the Relatives: A Dutch Nationwide Evaluation on Factors that Influence Consent Rates. *Neurocrit Care*. 2019;31(2):357-364. doi:10.1007/s12028-019-00678-8
10. Martínez-Soba F, Miñambres E, Martínez-Camarero L, et al. Results After Implementing a Program of Intensive Care to Facilitate Organ Donation. *Transplant Proc*. 2019;51(2):299-302. doi:10.1016/j.transproceed.2018.11.005
11. Martínez-Soba F, Pérez-Villares JM, Martínez-Camarero L, et al. Intensive Care to Facilitate Organ Donation: A Report on the Experience of 2 Spanish Centers with a Common Protocol. *Transplantation*. 2019;103(3):558-564. doi:10.1097/TP.0000000000002294
12. Krampe N, Nebra Puertas AC, Povar Echeverría M, Elmer J, Povar Marco J. Comparing demographics of organ donor referrals from the intensive care unit and outside units. *Transplant International*. 2021;34(11):2146-2153. doi:10.1111/tri.14001
13. Mazo C, Gómez A, Sandiumenge A, et al. Intensive Care to Facilitate Organ Donation: A Report on the 4-Year Experience of a Spanish Center With a Multidisciplinary Model to Promote Referrals Out of the Intensive Care Unit. *Transplant Proc*. 2019;51(9):3018-3026. doi:10.1016/j.transproceed.2019.08.025
14. Domínguez-Gil B, Coll E, Pont T, et al. End-of-life practices in patients with devastating brain injury in Spain: Implications for organ donation. *Medicina Intensiva (English Edition)*. 2017;41(3):162-173. doi:10.1016/j.medine.2017.03.003
15. Organización Nacional de Trasplantes. *Memoria Actividad Donación y Trasplante. España 2021. Organización Nacional de Trasplantes.; 2022.*

16. Escudero Augusto D, Martínez Soba F, de la Calle B, et al. Cuidados intensivos orientados a la donación de órganos. Recomendaciones ONT-SEMICYUC. *Med Intensiva*. 2021;45(4):234-242. doi:10.1016/J.MEDIN.2019.09.018
17. Martín-Delgado MC, Martínez-Soba F, Masnou N, et al. Summary of Spanish recommendations on intensive care to facilitate organ donation. *American Journal of Transplantation*. 2019;19(6):1782-1791. doi:10.1111/ajt.15253
18. SEMICYUC-ONT. *Cuidados intensivos orientados a la donación de órganos Recomendaciones Grupo de Trabajo [Intensive Care for Organ Donation. Taskforce recommendations] SEMICYUC-ONT*; 2017.
19. López JS, Soria-Oliver M, Aramayona B, García-Sánchez R, Martínez JM, Martín MJ. An Integrated Psychosocial Model of Relatives' Decision About Deceased Organ Donation (IMROD): Joining pieces of the puzzle. *Front Psychol*. 2018;9(APR):1-14. doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00408
20. López JS, Martínez JM, Soria-Oliver M, et al. Bereaved relatives' decision about deceased organ donation: An integrated psycho-social study conducted in Spain. *Soc Sci Med*. 2018;205(March):37-47. doi:10.1016/j.socscimed.2018.03.039
21. Soria-Oliver M, Aramayona B, López JS, et al. Grief Reactions of Potential Organ Donors' Bereaved Relatives: An Observational Study. *American Journal of Critical Care*. 2020;29(5):358-368. doi:10.4037/ajcc2020960
22. Kentish-Barnes N, Siminoff LA, Walker W, et al. A narrative review of family members' experience of organ donation request after brain death in the critical care setting. *Intensive Care Med*. 2019;45(3):331-342. doi:10.1007/s00134-019-05575-4
23. Miller C, Breakwell R. What factors influence a family's decision to agree to organ donation? A critical literature review. *London J Prim Care (Abingdon)*. 2018;10(4):103-107. doi:10.1080/17571472.2018.1459226
24. Chandler JA, Connors M, Holland G, Shemie SD. "effective" Requesting: A scoping review of the literature on asking families to consent to organ and tissue donation. *Transplantation*. 2017;101(5):S1-S16. doi:10.1097/TP.0000000000001695
25. de Groot J, Vernooij-Dassen M, Hoedemaekers C, Hoitsma A, Smeets W, van Leeuwen E. Decision Making by Relatives About Brain Death Organ Donation. An integrative review. *Transplantation*. 2012;93(12):1196-1211. doi:10.1097/TP.0b013e318256a45f
26. Simpkin AL, Robertson LC, Barber VS, Young JD. Modifiable factors influencing relatives' decision to offer organ donation: systematic review. *Bmj*. 2009;338.
27. Siminoff LA, Alolod GP, Wilson-Genderson M, Yuen EYN, Traino HM. A Comparison of Request Process and Outcomes in Donation After Cardiac Death and Donation After Brain Death: Results From a National Study. *American Journal of Transplantation*. 2017;17(5):1278-1285. doi:10.1111/ajt.14084
28. López JS. *Permisos y Negativas Familiares En La Donación de Órganos Para Trasplante: Un Estudio Psicosocial [Families' Consent and Refusal in Organ Donation For Transplantation: A Psychosocial Study]*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation . Universidad Autónoma de Madrid; 1997.

29. Vasileiou K, Barnett J, Thorpe S, Young T. Characterising and justifying sample size sufficiency in interview-based studies: Systematic analysis of qualitative health research over a 15-year period. *BMC Med Res Methodol*. 2018;18(1). doi:10.1186/s12874-018-0594-7
30. Weber RP. *Basic Content Analysis*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications; 1990.
31. Krippendorff K. *Content Analysis. An Introduction to Its Methodology*. 3rd ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications; 2004.
32. Fleiss JL, Levin B, Paik MC. *Statistical Methods for Rates and Proportions*. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons; 2013.
33. Altman DG. *Practical Statistics for Medical Research*. London, CRC Press; 1990.
34. Tong A, Sainsbury P, Craig J. Consolidated criteria for reporting qualitative research (COREQ): A 32-item checklist for interviews and focus groups. *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*. 2007;19(6):349-357. doi:10.1093/intqhc/mzm042
35. Matesanz R, Domínguez-Gil B, Coll E, de la Rosa G, Marazuela R. Spanish experience as a leading country: what kind of measures were taken? *Transplant International*. 2011;24(4):333-343.
36. Rodríguez-Arias D, Wright L, Paredes D. Success factors and ethical challenges of the Spanish Model of organ donation. *The Lancet*. 2010;376(9746):1109-1112.
37. DuBois JM, Anderson EE. Attitudes toward death criteria and organ donation among healthcare personnel and the general public. *Progress in Transplantation*. 2006;16(1):65-73.
38. Damar HT, Ordin YS, Top FÜ. Factors affecting attitudes toward organ donation in health care professionals. In: *Transplantation Proceedings*. Vol 51. Elsevier; 2019:2167-2170.
39. Silva e Silva V, Schirmer J, Roza BD, et al. Defining Quality Criteria for Success in Organ Donation Programs: A Scoping Review. *Can J Kidney Health Dis*. 2021;8. doi:10.1177/2054358121992921
40. Wojda TR SSYK et al. Keys to successful organ procurement: An experience-based review of clinical practices at a high-performing health-care organization. *Int J Crit Illn Inj Sci*. 2017;7(2):91-100.
41. Sque M, Walker W, Long-Sutehall T, Morgan M, Randhawa G, Rodney A. Bereaved donor families' experiences of organ and tissue donation, and perceived influences on their decision making. *J Crit Care*. 2018;45:82-89. doi:10.1016/j.jcrc.2018.01.002
42. López Martínez JS, Martín López MJ, Scandroglio B, Martínez García JM. Family Perception of the Process of Organ Donation. Qualitative Psychosocial Analysis of the Subjective Interpretation of Donor and Nondonor Families. *Spanish Journal of Psychology*. 2008;11(1):125-136. doi:10.1017/s1138741600004182
43. Kesselring A, Kainz M, Kiss A. Traumatic memories of relatives regarding brain death, request for organ donation and interactions with professionals in the ICU. *American Journal of Transplantation*. 2007;7(1):211-217. doi:10.1111/j.1600-6143.2006.01594.x

44. Gortmaker SL, Beasley CL, Sheehy E, et al. Improving the Request Process to Increase Family Consent for Organ Donation. *Journal of Transplant Coordination*. 1998;8(4):210-217. doi:10.1177/090591999800800404
45. Garrison RN, Bentley FR, Raque GH, et al. There is an answer to the shortage of organ donors. *Surg Gynecol Obstet*. 1991;173(5):391-396.
46. Martínez, JM, López, JS, Martín, A, Martín MJ, Scandroglio, B. Martín, JM. *Organ Donation and Family Decision-Making within the Spanish Donation System*. Vol 53.; 2001.
47. Weiss J, Coslovsky M, Keel I, Immer FF, Jüni P. Organ donation in Switzerland – An analysis of factors associated with consent rate. *PloS One*. 2014;9(9). Doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0106845
48. Siminoff LA, Lawrence RH, Zhang A. Decoupling: What is it and Does it Really Help Increase Consent to Organ Donation? *Progress in Transplantation*. 2002;12(1):52-60. Doi:10.1177/152692480201200110
49. Rodrigue JR, Cornell DL, Howard RJ. Does Family Disagreement Affect Donation Decisions by Next of Kin? *Progress in Transplantation*. 2008;18(3):179-184. Doi:10.1177/152692480801800306
50. Silva e Silva V, Schirmer J, Roza BD, et al. Defining Quality Criteria for Success in Organ Donation Programs: A Scoping Review. *Can J Kidney Health Dis*. 2021;8:2054358121992921.
51. Brinkmann S, Kvale S. *Doing Interviews*. Vol 2. Sage; 2018.
52. Gascón RM, Miranda B. *Organ Donation for Transplantation" the Spanish Model"*. Grupo Aula Medica; 1996.
53. Gómez P, Santiago C, Monino A, Dominguez JM. Obtención del consentimiento familiar para la donación. Relación de ayuda [Obtaining family consent for donation. Help Relationship]. *Revista Espanola de Trasplantes*. 1994;3:15-22.

TABLES

Table 1. Sample of transplant coordinator teams

Autonomous Community	Hospital	Number of ICOD donations in 2018 (per hospital)	Number of ICOD donations in 2018 (per stratum)	Number of total ICOD donations in 2018 (per autonomous community)
Andalusia	Hospital Universitario Virgen de la Macarena	14	35	102
	Hospital Universitario Reina Sofía	11		
	Hospital Regional Universitario de Málaga	10		
Aragon	Hospital Universitario Miguel Servet	18	18	23
Asturias	Hospital Universitario Central de Asturias	24	24	24
Balearic Islands	Hospital Universitario Son Espases	26	26	26
Canary Islands	Hospital de Gran Canarias Dr. Negrin	10	15	47
	Hospital Universitario Insular de Gran Canaria	5		
Cantabria	Hospital Universitario Marqués de Valdecilla	6	6	6
Castile-La Mancha	Hospital Universitario Virgen de la Salud	6	6	34
Castile-León	Complejo Asistencial de Burgos	10	10	27
Catalonia	Hospital Universitario Vall D Hebron	24	52	92
	Hospital Universitario de Gerona Dr Josep Trueta	28		
Extremadura	Hospital Infanta Cristina	22	22	22
Galicia	Complejo Hospitalario Universitario de Santiago de Compostela	32	32	44
La Rioja	Hospital San Pedro	12	12	12
Madrid	Hospital Universitario Gregorio Marañón	24	52	60
	Hospital Universitario Ramon y Cajal	18		
	Hospital Universitario de la Princesa	10		
Murcia	Hospital Universitario Virgen de la Arrixaca	13	13	13
Navarre	Hospital Universitario de Navarra	26	26	26
Basque Country	Hospital Universitario de Araba	14	14	31
Valencia	Hospital Universitario Dr Balmis	8	8	29
	TOTAL (23 hospitals)	371		

Note: ICOD, intensive care to facilitate organ donation.

Table 2. Identification of ICOD candidates

Percentage of cases wherein identifying potential ICOD candidates was difficult	
None	5
Almost none	9
10–20%	3
Cannot estimate	6
Difficulties perceived by TCTs in identifying ICOD candidates	Cases
Limited familiarity with or awareness of ICOD among professionals in other units	8
Apparent medical contraindications	5
Advanced age of the potential donor (which does not necessarily hinder organ donation)	3
Uncertainty regarding prognosis	3
Unknown clinical antecedents	2
Inaccurate assessment by the medical staff	2

Note: TCT, transplant coordination team; ICOD, intensive care to facilitate organ donation.

Table 3. EI preparation by TCTs

Objectives	Cases
Ensuring the family's understanding and acceptance of the patient's situation	8
Offering emotional support to the family	5
Obtaining donors	5
Absence of specific objectives	2
Ensuring admission to the ICU in case of consent	2
Gathering main family characteristics	2
Providing a dignified family treatment	1
Ensuring that the patient does not suffer	1
Ensuring that the family does not suffer	1
Feeling satisfaction with the work conducted	1
Preparation strategies	
<i>Emotional preparation</i>	
Achieving a calm state	3
Seeking compassion in themselves	1
Becoming aware that the death of a patient can have a positive aspect	1
Developing a mental dialogue to avoid anxiety	1
Approaching the situation positively	1
Achieving self-awareness and accepting the emotions that arise (mindfulness)	1
<i>Technical actions</i>	
Ensuring the availability of space for performing the interview	10
Collecting family and patient information	9
Reviewing the patient's fulfillment of the conditions for donation	6
Preparing the EI speech	2
Scheduling an appropriate amount of time to attend to the family	1
Ensuring that the family emotional intensity decreases	1
Ensuring the availability of free beds in the ICU	1
<i>Coordination with other health personnel</i>	
Seeking general information	15
Ensuring that the family has been informed of the clinical status of the patient before starting the EI	8
Introducing the transplant coordinator to the relatives, performed by the patient's primary physician	5
Conducting the interview with other health personnel other than the coordinator	4
Ensuring that interviewers involve both physicians and nurses	2
Explicitly establishing a communication strategy	2
Establishing a strategy of action according to the family's response	1
Ensuring that the family has been able to visit the patient	1
Ensuring that the family has been informed by the physician about patient situation	1
Admitting the patient into the ICU before starting the interview with the family	1
Obtaining agreement on the speech to the family from other physicians	1

Note: EI, early interview; ICU, intensive care unit.

Table 4. TCT strategies to determine the potential donor's last will regarding donation

	Cases
Review the last will register before performing the EI	16
Inquire with the family directly	
Ask about patients' will regarding donation or transplantation	7
Ask if they had talked about donation in the family	6
Ask about the patient's general moral or ethical characteristics	2
Ask for documents in which the patient expressed their opinion on their death	1
Ask about specific moral or ethical characteristics, citing positive characteristics	1

Note: EI, early interview.

Table 5. Strategies for initiating EIs with families: verbal and non-verbal behavior

	Cases
<i>Verbal behavior</i>	
Explaining the fatal prognosis and possibility of donating	19
Introducing themselves to the family	15
Confirming the family's understanding and resolving doubts	10
Identification of decision makers and their relationship with the patient and addressing those closest to the patient	7
Ensuring comfort and assessing family needs	7
Empathizing with the relatives' situation	6
Tailoring the message to interviewees	4
Indicating that the donor/s comfort will be ensured	3
Offering condolences	3
Offering help	2
Adapting the message to the family situation (ethical or sociocultural)	2
Talking about donation before ICOD	1
Asking what the patient represents for the family	1
Requesting consent for intubation	1
Ensuring that relatives will be able to be with the patient as much as possible	1
Calming the family's worries and sense of guilt	1
Confirming with family the withdrawal of all therapeutic measures if desired	1
Linking previous catastrophic prognosis information with dignified death	1
Adapting the way of treating patient's relatives to their characteristics	1
Assessing decision-making capacity	1
<i>Non-verbal behavior</i>	
Maintaining physical contact and closeness according to the characteristics or needs of the family	10
Taking care of personal distance and ensuring that everyone is seated	9
Maintaining eye contact	4
Sensitivity in the way of expressing oneself	3
Wearing a lab coat	2
Maintaining silences	2
Adopting the same body position as the family	2
Reacting honestly	2
Staying calm	2
Expressing worry and sadness	1
Avoiding physical barriers	1
Maintaining some distance in contact and emotional expression (avoiding emotional contagion)	1
Using of drawings as support	1
Accompanying words with gestures	1
Observing, developing an approach, and assessing the approach	1

Attending to the attitudes of the people present	1
Paying attention to who speaks first and last in the family	1
Listening	1

Note: EI, early interview; ICOD, intensive care to facilitate organ donation.

Table 6. TCT strategies for EI development

	Cases
Informing and solving doubts	14
Consulting the patient's will and family's desire	8
Establishing relationships and addressing initial concerns	6
Ensuring patient comfort	5
Selecting the moment in which the interview is conducted	5
Allowing relatives time to process the information and be able to make the decision	4
Prompting relatives to reflect on what the patient was like in life	4
Allowing the family to express themselves	4
Separating the decision to donate from the potential discomfort of relatives with the health system	3
Emotional accompaniment	2
Promoting a sense of comfort and freedom of decision	2
Identifying and addressing the most favorable family member	2
Teamwork between several interviewers	2
Emphasizing that the patient is special	2
Selecting the moments in which the information is given	2
Avoiding corporatism	1
Facilitating the family being present when life support is limited	1
Asking the family if they know someone who received a transplant	1
Ensuring that the EI is conducted by a physician other than the one who reported the clinical situation	1
Ensuring that the relatives are continuously kept informed	1
Helping the family understand the patient's situation	1
Selecting the moment of when broach the donation topic	1

Note: EI, early interview

Table 7. Arguments used for EI development

	Cases
Explaining the possibility of helping other people in need	19
Alluding to what the patient would have wanted	14
Raising donation as a right that can be chosen (not an obligation), which few families have	9
Pointing out that donation could help cope with grief	8
Pointing out that donation allows better conditions and more time to say goodbye to the patient	3
Pointing out that donations is rewarding over time	3
Emphasizing the irreversibility of the clinical situation	2
Helping relatives empathize with people who could benefit from transplantation	2
Alluding to the family's generosity	1
Emphasizing the absence of positive consequences for the family and patient if donation is denied	1
Assuring the family that they can stand by the patient	1
Describing one's own and that of other families in the same situation	1
Delinking the decision from the potential discomfort with the care received	1
Pointing out that donation does not cause harm to family members or the patients	1
Offering the possibility of performing an autopsy that reduces doubts about the care received	1

Note: EI, early interview

Table 8. Indicators of denial of consent and strategies used by TCTs to cope with them

Indicators of denial of consent	Cases
Expression of discontent with the healthcare system	5
Non-verbal language with an elusive look	4
Low socio-economic/educational level or not belonging to the national context of the hospital	4
Lack of understanding of the irreversible state of the relative	3
Anger shown by relatives before the coordinator contacted the family	3
Lack of acceptance of the fatal prognosis	2
Physical distancing	2
Non-verbal denial (head shaking)	2
Not listening	2
TCT strategies to cope with denial of consent indicators	
Offering a wider time margin to make the decision	7
Referring to the possible beneficiaries of the donation	7
Trying to solve possible doubts	6
Asking about the refusal arguments	6
Alluding to the patient's virtues and lifestyle and relating them to the virtues of donation and transplantation	4
Ensuring respect for the donor's body and image	4
Allowing the relatives to physically stand by the patient as long as they want	3
Promoting the questioning of donor's negative will regarding donation or transplantation	3
Relying on a family member to promote consent	3
Searching for religious figures or documentation that facilitates the understanding of the process	3
Alluding to transplant cases known by the family	2
Entering into explicit refutation of the family refusal (arguments and emotions)	2
Separating family members to talk individually	2
Not including family members who may represent a problem in the interview	1
Asking family members how they feel	2
Agreeing with family members in the face of their anger	1
Encouraging the family to talk about the donation if they have not done so before	1
Pointing out the opportunity for the patient to do something good	1
Asking the relatives to place themselves in the position of a potential beneficiary	1
In case of family conflict, prioritizing the expressed or assumed opinion of the potential donor about donation and transplantation	1
In case of family conflict, expecting the family members to relegate their conflicts outside the ICU and focus on the application for ICOD	1
Ensuring patient comfort	1
Assuring family members that the decision can be reversed whenever they wish	1

Assuring family members that any mistakes will be reviewed (in case of complaints from them regarding how the case was handled)	1
---	---

Note: ICOD, intensive care to facilitate organ donation; ICU, intensive care unit; TCT, transplant coordination team.

Table 9. Events and actions between ICOD implementation and effective donation

	Cases
Events that could alter family consent	
Family's perception that the waiting time until death was excessive	7
Arrival of relatives after the interview who press for denial of consent	4
Family suffering	2
Change of decision if the family's expectations about staying and visiting the potential donor were not met	1
Shift toward serenity and realization of family encounters after the initial impact	1
Emergence of family conflict	1
Emergence of family doubts regarding the patient's death	1
Need for control on the part of the family	1
Need for the family member to finish as soon as possible	1
External pressure, such as from neighbors and acquaintances	1
Actions mentioned by TCTs in case of delayed death	
Proposal for CDCDD	10
Limitation and withdrawal of life support	7
Explaining the situation and ensuring that the family understands it	4
Asking the family to wait longer	4
Transferring the patient to another hospital unit outside the ICU	3
Informing the family of various possibilities	3
Informing the family that comfort measures are maintained	2
Offering the family the possibility to physically accompanying the patient	2
Providing special attention to relatives	2
Transferring the patient to a hospital center for chronically ill patients	1
Providing the coordinator's telephone number to address possible doubts	1
Respecting the ritual of "saying goodbye" to the patient	1
Striving to satisfy special needs or requests of the family	1

Note: CDCDD, controlled donation after the circulatory determination of death; ICOD, intensive care to facilitate organ donation; TCT, transplant coordination team.

Table 10. TCTs' perceptions of the final reasons for family refusal and percentage of cases wherein family consent was obtained upon ICOD request

Reasons for family refusal	Cases
Negative will of the potential donor	16
Ignorance of the will of the potential donor	9
Desire to maintain bodily integrity	6
Religious beliefs	4
Family decision	4
Desire not to prolong the process	3
Revenge against the social/health system	3
General fatigue	3
Arguing that a family member who is not present does not want to donate	2
Avoiding suffering of the potential donor	2
Problems with the health system	2
Lack of time to assimilate the situation	2
Belief that the probability of death is not certain	1
Anger	1
Family's cultural customs	1
Donor's advanced age	1
Previous bad experience with donation	1
Percentage of cases in which consent was obtained	
90–100%	7
70–89%	8
50–69%	3
<50%	1
No data/unknown (4)	4

Note: ICOD, intensive care to facilitate organ donation; ICU, intensive care unit; TCT, transplant coordination team.

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1. Global view of the phases, pathways, and potential outcomes involved in the ICOD procedure

Notes:

¹ Minimum conditions for the EI:

- Relevant decision makers are present
- Family has been informed regarding the irreversible state of their relative
- Emotional state of decision makers allows the discussion regarding potential organ donation.

² Preliminary consent for implementing MV:

- MV facilitates the maintenance of donation possibilities until favorable conditions for the development of the EI for ICOD request exist.

MV is typically necessary in emergency admissions, at night, and when only isolated family are present.

Request of permission for MV implementation is performed with whatever family member who is present

It is emphasized to relatives that the authorization-is provisional, reversible, and intended to maintain the possibilities for the whole family to decide.

³ Conditions that are agreed upon with relatives:

- Decision is provisional and reversible at any moment.
- Maximum waiting time period until evolution to BD occurs (generally 24–72 hours).

BD, brain death; CDCDD, controlled donation after the circulatory determination of death; DBD, donation after brain death; EI, early interview; ICOD, intensive care to facilitate organ donation; ICU, intensive care unit; TCT, transplant coordination team; MV, mechanical ventilation; SM, support measure.

Figure 2. First-level prefigured coding structure

